

Information System Analysis and Design (September 2021)

Puji Rahmadhani, Department of Industrial Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Universitas Andalas, Padang, West Sumatra, Indonesia

Abstract—An information system is a system that connects the daily transaction processing needs, operations support, management activities and strategies within an organization to provide the required reports, both for certain internal and external parties. An information system is the result of human design and consists of various components within an organization to achieve a goal, namely to provide useful information. Information system is one of the aspects needed by the organization. The progress or decline of an organization is represented by the effectiveness and efficiency of the information systems used by the organization. The design of information systems for business begins with redesigning existing business processes. The implementation of web-based applications opens up opportunities for increasing process efficiency, so the redesign is aimed at simplifying business processes. There are some related things within information system discipline such as System Development Life Cycle (SDLC), Rapid Application Development (RAD) and Computer-Aided Software Engineering (CASE), Agile Methodologies and Extreme Programming, Object-oriented Analysis and design the Rational Unified Process (RUP).

Index Terms—Analysis, Information, System, System Information

I. INTRODUCTION

The effectiveness and efficiency of information systems is a key aspect that can determine the progress and setbacks of an organization. An effective and properly implemented information system will affect management performance in controlling the production system of the manufacturing industry. However, information systems that are too complex and complicated can reduce the efficiency of the production system as a whole.

Web-based applications are often used to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of a process. Examples of its application are quite broad, such as increasing efficiency in the learning process, consumption of electrical energy at home, as well as in collecting survey data. The increase in efficiency occurs because web-based applications make it easier for actors involved in the system to carry out their tasks. [1]

Information system analysis and design is one of the disciplines related to information systems. Information systems analysis and design is a complex organizational process that is used to develop and maintain computer-based information systems also used by a team of business and system

professionals. Information systems analysis and design is important to study because it can ease human work because it uses technology with advanced and automated systems.

The purpose of writing this journal is because there are still many people who do not understand this information systems analysis and design even though the benefits are very many, so it is hoped that this journal can help add insight to its readers.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. System

System is a collection of several elements or elements that interact with each other to achieve a certain goal. In addition, the system can also be said as a network of interconnected work to carry out an activity or complete certain goals. Systems can be groups of people, machines, things or other types of entities.

A system can also be interpreted as a collection of elements in the form of data, a network of interconnected procedures, human resources, technology, both hardware and software that interact as a single unit to achieve the same specific goals or objectives. A system itself can consist of several subsystems, namely the payroll accounting subsystem, the cost subsystem, and so on.

A system must meet the minimum requirements, namely to have 3 elements that make up the system, consisting of input, process, and output. The following is the simplest form of the system:

Fig. 1. System Life Cycle

Input is data or information needed by a system for further processing in accordance with the provisions of the process. In the end the system will produce output which if needed again then the output will return to an input, and so on, this is called as the system life cycle. [2]

Systems Analysis is a process of collecting and interpreting facts, identifying the problems, and decomposition of a system into its components. System analysis is conducted for the purpose of studying a system or its parts in order to identify its objectives. It is a problem-solving technique that improves the

system and ensures that all the components of the system work efficiently to accomplish their purpose.

Systems Design is a process of planning a new business system or replacing an existing system by defining its components or modules to satisfy the specific requirements. Before planning, you need to understand the old system thoroughly and determine how computers can best be used in order to operate efficiently. System Design focuses on how to accomplish the objective of the system.

B. Information

Information can be defined as the result of data processing that has a certain value or meaning. Information is data that is processed into a form that is more useful and meaningful to the recipient. Source of information is data. Reality data that describes an event and a real entity. Events are events that occur at a certain time. [3]

Data that is processed to produce information can use a certain process model. For example, the temperature in Fahrenheit is converted to Celsius. In this case, a mathematical model is used in the form of a conversion formula from degrees Fahrenheit to units of degrees Celsius. The data that is processed through a model becomes information, then the recipient receives the information, which means making decisions and taking other actions that will make some data back.

C. System Information

An information system is a system that connects the daily transaction processing needs, operations support, management activities and strategies within an organization to provide the required reports, both for certain internal and external parties.

There are several definitions of information systems according to experts including the following [4]:

1. According to Yakub (2012), the information system is a collection of components within the organization associated with the process of creating the flow of information.
2. According to Ida Nuraida (2008), the information system is a set of procedures that are systematically organized, if implemented, will provide information that can be utilized in the decision-making process.

A computer-based information system (CBIS) in an organization consists of the following components:

1. Hardware, which is a component to complete the activities of entering data, processing data, and outputting data.
2. Software, programs and instructions given to a computer.
3. Database, which is a collection of data and information organized in such a way that it is easily accessible to users of the information system.
4. Telecommunications, namely communication that connects system users with computer systems together into an effective work network.
5. Humans, namely personnel from information systems, including managers, analysts, programmers, and

operators, and are responsible for system maintenance. [3]

Procedures, namely procedures that include strategies, policies, methods, and regulations in using computer-based information systems.

III. DISCUSSION

The Industrial Revolution 4.0 provides several benefits for society; provide opportunities for companies and research institutions to actively shape the future. The economic impact of this industrial revolution should be enormous, because Industry 4.0 promises to substantially increase operational effectiveness as well as the development of very new (not yet available) business models, services and new products. Likewise with the development of increasingly rapid information systems.

An information system is the result of human design and consists of various components within an organization to achieve a goal, namely to provide useful information. Information system is one of the aspects needed by the organization. The progress or decline of an organization is represented by the effectiveness and efficiency of the information systems used by the organization.

The general objectives of the information system include: (1) Providing information that can assist the management decision-making process; (2) Facilitate the implementation of daily operations; and (3) Providing appropriate information for parties outside the organization, especially regarding the issue of management transparency. [5]

Information systems must be able to support the company's business strategy. The business strategy is realized through a series of business processes, so that the ideal business process is the foundation for the development of information systems. Business processes describe all activities carried out in a system. Inputs, processes, outputs, actors involved, data and information flows can be identified through the description of business processes. In addition to these descriptions, business processes also provide explanations regarding the activities involved and their relationships in achieving system goals and producing outputs. Representation of business processes in the form of images is a Business Process Diagram.

The design of information systems begins with redesigning existing business processes. The implementation of web-based applications opens up opportunities for increasing process efficiency, so the redesign is aimed at simplifying business processes.

The design of the new information system is carried out to develop the existing information system. The design process is carried out by building [1]:

1. Business process diagram
2. Use case diagram
3. Class diagram
4. Entity Relationship Diagram
5. Database

For example, A study on improving warehousing management through the implementation of a warehousing information system, in making information systems for this

study, the tools used are document flow diagrams, data flow diagrams. While the information design is through input or output design, the database design software used is PHP7 & MySQL, and for making ERD using case tools software. [6]

Information systems are also very helpful for a business in the field of marketing. The development of information technology allows people around the world to exchange information with an unlimited number of transactions and can be accessed anytime and anywhere. The role of the internet for marketing products and services provides benefits and a positive impact on business sustainability. Marketing of products or services online aims to facilitate sales so as to reduce expenses such as advertising costs and the cost of making brochures. New innovations in digital business have opened up opportunities for transformation in marketing information systems that used to be offline to online. This form of online marketing provides a great opportunity for companies to expand market segmentation without the limitations of space and time. [7]

The rapid development of technology in the information age has increased the intensity of competition in the business world. This also has an effect on SCM where business competition has shifted from competition between companies to competition between supply chains. One of the goals of SCM is to manage and improve the flow of materials from the point of origin to the point of delivery as well as information feedback from the end consumer at the lowest possible cost. Good, integrated and transparent flow of information from suppliers to end consumers. The flow of information can be managed properly if a good information system design is used as well. [8]

There are some related things within information system discipline such as System Development Life Cycle (SDLC), Rapid Application Development (RAD) and Computer-Aided Software Engineering (CASE), Agile Methodologies and Extreme Programming, Object-oriented Analysis and design the Rational Unified Process (RUP).

The SDLC is a process model that describes and prescribes the phases that have to (or at least should) be carried out in the process of developing an information system for specific usage situations. There are several potential strengths of the SDLC, it is simple and easy to understand; it is well established; there exist methodological support; it includes concrete deliverables and milestone, and support tools for each phase.

Rapid application development is an agile software development approach that focuses more on ongoing software projects and user feedback and less on following a strict plan. As such, it emphasizes rapid prototyping over costly planning. Computer-aided software engineering (CASE) is the domain of software tools used to design and implement applications. CASE tools are similar to and were partly inspired by computer-aided design (CAD) tools used for designing hardware products. CASE tools are used for developing high-quality, defect-free, and maintainable software. CASE software is often associated with methods for the development of information systems together with automated tools that can be used in the software development process.

Rational Unified Process (RUP) is a software development

process framework created by Rational Software Corporation. RUP provides guides, templates, and examples of all aspects of the information systems development stage. There are three perspectives in the RUP, namely Dynamic Perspective and Lifecycle Phases, Static Perspective, and Practice Perspective and Core Process.

IV. CONCLUSION

System is a collection of several elements or elements that interact with each other to achieve a certain goal. A system can also be interpreted as a collection of elements in the form of data, a network of interconnected procedures, human resources, technology, both hardware and software that interact as a single unit to achieve the same specific goals or objectives. A system must meet the minimum requirements, namely to have 3 elements that make up the system, consisting of input, process, and output.

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